

Carbon electrodes for bio-electricity generation in microbial fuel cells

Praveena Mishra, Shraddha Sharma and Rajeev Jain*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : rajeevjain54@yahoo.co.in, praveena.mica2011@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 10 March 2017, accepted 11 March 2017

Abstract : Experiments carried out to find out optimum experimental conditions and electrode materials have been compiled with conventional carbon materials i.e. CC, GrR, CP and WC by taking in a microbial fuel cell setup as anode to select the best electrodes material among these. Dual chamber MFC filled with sewage wastewater as substrate was used for the comparative study of current and power production using different anode materials. The electrochemical properties of the electrodes have been investigated by cyclic voltammetry. During power production, stability of anodes along with COD, BOD removal efficiencies were also calculated. The SEM images taken after 45 days of the experiment confirm biocompatibility of anodes. The comparative study suggest better results with CC anode as compared to other anode materials.

Keywords : Microbial fuel cells, mixed sewage culture, carbon electrode, chemical oxygen demand (COD).

Introduction

Microbial fuel cells (MFCs) are the electrochemical devices that can convert the chemical energy in to electrical energy by means of direct oxidation of living organisms because, it enables direct transfer of chemical energy stored in a biodegradable organic matter into bio-electricity¹⁻⁵. MFCs become one of the emerging technologies in the field of environmental protection and energy recovery. The anode material, cathode material, proton exchange membrane and microorganisms are the major components of the MFCs. The improvements in these components are essential for the development of this self sustainable technology. In last decade good progress has been observed in the performance of MFC⁶⁻⁸. Future applications of MFCs include bio-electricity generation, wastewater treatment, desalination, chemical production and biosensor applications^{9,10}. The output and columbic efficiency are significantly affected by the MFC configuration and operating condition. Currently real word application of MFCs is limited due to its low power density. Attempts are being made to improve the power generation and limiting factors like nature of electrode materials, chemical substances,

microbial inoculum, reactor design distance of the electrodes, ionic strength, internal and external resistances, the presence or absence of a proton exchange membrane and catalyst properties^{11,12}. Chemical and electrochemical stability as well as bio-fouling and insensitivity against poisoning by biological products are being investigated.

As a consequential part of MFCs, a high performance of electrode material is most essential to improve the power out-put of MFCs, to make them commercialize for energy generation and alter the bacterial loading and electron transfer. A material with high specific surface area is desirable for both catalytic processes and could play an important role for improving the MFC power density. Such a structure needs to host the bacteria with high biocompatibility while enhanced the electron transfer rate¹³⁻¹⁸. The anode material and its structure can directly affect the bacterial growth, rate of electron transfer and COD removal efficiency¹⁹. Carbon materials are applied in most MFC applications as anode, due to their stability in harnessing condition of anodic chamber²⁰⁻²². These carbon materials do not show good electro-catalytic activity for the anodic microbial growth and the addition of

mediators are required for improving MFCs performances.

Since electrodes play an important role in MFCs technology for electricity generation, carbon materials, such as carbon cloth and felt, plain graphite, sponge carbon, graphite granules and carbon paper have been widely used as anode materials in MFC, because of their good stability in microbial inoculums mixture, low charge transfer resistance, high conductivity and specific surface area²³⁻²⁹. Power production in MFCs is limited because of the carcinogenic conditions for the electrode in anodic compartment. In this work carbon cloth, graphite rod, wire cloth and carbon paper have been used as anode material to monitor power production during treatment of sewage wastewater. Two chamber microbial fuel cell experiments were carried out to demonstrate the efficiency of wastewater for power production in different experimental conditions.

In this context, the study of interaction between different anode materials and microorganisms represents a new and interesting research to investigate the stability and biocompatibility of the conventional electrode materials. For comparative study four different anode materials i.e. carbon cloth (CC), graphite rod (GrR), carbon paper (CP) and wire cloth (WC) were taken and used for study in dual chamber MFC for the treatment of wastewater and producing electricity at the same time. The results of power density (PD),

current density (CD) and COD, BOD removal efficiency of conventional electrodes have been compared while generating electricity from sewage waste.

Results and discussion

Performance evaluation of electrodes :

The effect of electrodes on power production in different MFCs was evaluated by open circuit voltage measurements using dual chamber MFC. The current density and power density measurements of MFCs with different electrodes are shown in Fig. 1. For all types of anodes under study power production was observed. Current and voltage increases with time and the highest power production were achieved after 7th day of incubation. It was found that the highest PD $792.08 \pm 0.7 \text{ mW m}^{-2}$ and CD $199 \pm 0.8 \text{ mA m}^{-2}$ was achieved for CC followed by GrR with a PD $584.82 \pm 0.6 \text{ mW m}^{-2}$ and CD $171 \pm 0.7 \text{ mA m}^{-2}$ respectively. Power density measurement by CP and WC was $300.12 \pm 0.8 \text{ mW m}^{-2}$ and $165.62 \pm 0.9 \text{ mW m}^{-2}$ respectively. Current density calculated for CP and WC was $122 \pm 0.6 \text{ mA m}^{-2}$ and $91 \pm 0.8 \text{ mA m}^{-2}$ respectively. The better current and power measurement with CC is attributed due to the porous structure of CC. It provides large surface area to better attachment of bacteria.

Electrochemical characterization :

The electrochemical responses of all electrodes were

Fig. 1. Current densities and power densities conventional anodes after 30 days operation of MFC setups. [A] Current densities (A m^{-2}) of anode CC (a), GrR (b), CP (c) and WC (d). [B] Power densities (mW m^{-2}) of anodes CC (a), GrR (b), CP (c) and WC (d).

characterized by cyclic voltammetry (CV). Cyclic voltammetry was employed to investigate the electrochemical changes on electrodes in 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ solution by applying potential from -0.2 to 0.6 V at the scan rate of 50 mV s^{-1} . As shown in Fig. 2Ad CV of CC electrode were obtained increment in redox peak current of $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ as compared to WC (Fig. 2Aa), CP (Fig. 2Ab) and GrR (Fig. 2Ac). These results were observed as excellent electron conducting on the surface of CC electrode to redox solution.

In order to evaluate the effect of scan rate on the CC electrode a CV at different scan rates were re-

corded (Fig. 2B). As the scan rate is increased from 10 to 100 mV s^{-1} at a definite concentration of electrolyte, the peak potential shifted towards more positive potential. A plot between the peak current (i_p) and the square root of the scan rate ($v^{1/2}$) is linear (Fig. 2C) for the CC, which suggests that the reaction occurring on the electrode surface is nearly reversible and also confirm the diffusion controlled behaviour of electrode^{34,35}. The linear dependence of the peak current on scan rate can be expressed by the eq. (i) :

$$i_p(A) = 0.811 (v^{1/2}, V s^{-1})C - 0.761; \quad (i)$$

$$r^2 = 0.996$$

The effective surface area of working electrodes plays

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms recorded in 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ containing 0.1 M KCl as electrolyte solution at different electrodes WC (a), CP (b), GrR (c) and CC (d) [A]; Cyclic voltammograms of the CC at different scan rates (0.01–0.1 V/s) [B]; Represents linearity curves at different scan rates [C].

an important role during modification of an electrode because it directly influences their sensitivity. Electro active surface area was calculate for all four electrodes by using Randles-Sevick equation³⁶.

$$i_p = 2.69 \times 10^5 AD^{1/2} n^{3/2} \nu^{1/2} C \quad (\text{ii})$$

The obtained average value of electro active surface area for CC, GrR, CP and WC electrodes was (5.897 cm²), (1.809 cm²), (1.748 cm²) and (2.667 cm²) respectively. It clearly demonstrates that CC is having the larger surface area as compared to other conventional electrode material. These results suggest that CC plays an important role in enhancing the MFC technology.

Stability measurements :

The stability of electrode is a limiting factor in MFC performance³⁷. MFC application required a material with high stability, good selectivity and efficiency. The ideal property of anode material should have large potential range, low resistance and reproducible surface. In each spike of current generation was followed by refueling of MFC reactor with new substrate, resulting in the next cycle of the power generation. For the first cycles of CC anode highest PD achieved was 792.00 mW/cm² at 7th day of incubation. When it reached to back ground current fresh substrate that is sewage wastewater with mix bacterium culture was added. For the second cycle of CC anode highest PD 648.00 mW/cm² was achieved at 7th day of incubation and for third cycle power density was decreased to 480.5 mW/cm² after completion of third cycle current reach to lower limit. On the basis of results obtained we can conclude that CC anode showed stability upto 90 days for MFC application. Decrease in highest PD was observed for CC (311 mW/cm²). As the values were lower than that value of (2.88 mW/cm²) MFC setup was stopped after 90 days.

Bio-compatibility of electrode :

The better output of density of the MFCs can be achieved by the development of good number of bacterial colonies on the surfaces of anodes. To test the bio-compatibility of anodes, toxicity was studied by SEM analysis after completion of MFC experiment. Fig. 3 displays the SEM results after 30 days of MFC

experiments for all 4 types of anodes used in the experiment. No toxicity was observed on surface of anodes in SEM images which confirmed bio-compatibility of the electrodes. The electrodes under study are non toxic for the bacteria and supporting the growth of the culture. WC and CP electrodes show poor growth of bacteria (Fig. 3C and 3D) as compared to GrR electrode (Fig. 3B). The CC surface (Fig. 3A) displays best growth as compared to other electrodes used in this study. The SEM results demonstrated that a good amount of bacteria was attached on CC surface.

Conductivity measurements :

To test the conductivity of electrode with respect to increase in resistance i-V characterization of CC anode was measured at different time intervals. The i-V plot of fresh CC showing ohmic behaviour and resistivity of 1.69 Ω lies in semiconducting range (Fig. 4A). After completion of first cycle and second cycle resistance of CC anode was 1.86 Ω and 2.4 Ω respectively (Fig. 4B and 4C). The observed increase in resistance indicated degradation of CC.

COD removal efficiency :

Besides power generation, contaminant removal is another criteria to evaluate MFCs. During operation all four mediator less MFCs were tested with sewage wastewater (as COD) removal to enumerate the potential of fuel cell to act as wastewater treatment unit. All MFCs showed their potential for COD removal indicating the function of microbes, present in wastewaters in metabolizing the carbon source as electron donors³⁸. It is evident from experimental data that current generation and COD removal showed relative compatibility. The COD removal efficiency of the different MFCs was higher than 64%. MFC is the proper tool for the reduction of COD, as well as electricity generation. The results in Table 1 show that the COD removal efficiency of all MFCs devices.

Experimental

Chemicals and materials :

Carbon cloth (CC), graphite rod (GrR), carbon paper (CP) and wire cloth (WC), platinum powder and proton exchange membrane (PEM) Nafion 117 were procured from Fuel Cell Store (US). K₃[Fe(CN)₆] was purchased from Merck and connections of MFC

Fig. 3. SEM images of the microbes attached on the surface of CC [A], GrR [B], CP [C], WC [D].

set-up were made using titanium wire purchased from local market. All solutions and supporting electrolytes were of analytical grade and prepared using ultra pure water. Double distilled water from distillation assembly was used for necessary dilutions.

Instrumentation :

The electrochemical experiments of all electrodes were performed with a CH-Instrument (Model 660B electrochemical workstation). All experiments performed using three electrode cell, a platinum plate as a counter electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and four different electrodes as working electrode. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) study were carried out in 5 mM $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]/K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ containing 0.1 M KCl solution. All the solutions were examined by the electrochemical technique after purging with purified nitrogen gas for 10 min, subsequently

a regular stream of nitrogen was passed over the solutions during measurements. Current-voltage (i-V) characterization was done by two probe method. In order to make i-V observation contacts are taken on the electrode with the help of silver paint to which a DC voltage power supply was connected. Voltmeter was placed in parallel to the electrode and ammeter in series with the fuel cell circuit, resistance of electrode could be evaluated from the slope of i-V graph. A JEOL ISM 840 scanning electron microscope (SEM) after coating with gold at 5 KV was used for SEM characterization. A magnetic stirrer controller (Model TH-100 Spectra lab, India) was employed for controlling the stirring speed. Sonication was done by using sonicator (Fisher FS110). Digital multi meter (Philips DM 334) was used to monitor current and potential from the MFC set-up. The pH of the solutions was measured by us-

Fig. 4. Current-voltage (i-V) characteristics of the CC electrode : (A) i-V plot of fresh CC, (B) i-V plot of CC after completion of first cycle and (C) i-V plot of CC after completion of second cycle.

Table 1. Wastewater characteristics with different electrodes used in the study

Anode	Current density (A m ⁻²)	Power density (mW m ⁻²)	COD removal (%)	CE (%)
CC	1.99±0.8	792.08±0.7	85.11	20
GrR	1.71±0.7	584.82±0.6	78.32	18
CP	1.22±0.6	300.12±0.8	69.54	14
WC	0.91±0.8	165.62±0.9	64.56	11

ing pH meter Systronic Decibel Instrument DB-1011.

MFC construction :

MFC was constructed in the laboratory using two rectangular boxes [7.7 cm×16 cm×4.6 cm] for a total volume of around 400 mL and working volume of 250 mL. The anode chamber was sealed to maintain

an aerobic environment. Both anode and cathode were separated by proton exchange membrane (Nafion 117 diameter 2.0 cm) having diameter 2.0 cm. It was subjected to sequentially pre-treatment in 30% H₂O₂ for 45 min followed in 1.0 M H₂SO₄ for 45 min and finally washed with de-ionized water for 15 min to increase the porosity of the membrane and was fixed between clamps connecting both the chambers. The working dimensions for CC was length of ~2 cm, width 1 cm, height 1 mm, GrR had length of ~2 cm, width 1 cm and height of 20 mm, CP with a length of ~2 cm, width 1 cm, height 1 mm and WC had a length of ~2 cm, width 1 cm and height 1 mm. The distance between the floating anode and the cathodic carbon cloth was 4 cm. Anaerobic mixed bacterial culture was used as parent culture in the anodic cham-

ber and the volume was 100 mL. The anodic chamber was continuously flushed with N₂ gas to maintain anaerobic conditions. The cathode chamber was filled with 50 mL phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 solutions with 0.5 g K₃[Fe(CN)₆]. The cathode was continuously flushed with O₂ gas to maintain aerobic conditions. Oxygen was used as electron acceptor for the electrode.

Inoculation and operation :

Sewage wastewater collected from Swarn Rekha, Gwalior (Madhya Pradesh), India was used as the inoculums for all MFC tests and kept in a refrigerator at 4 °C before use. Parent culture was enriched in designed synthetic wastewater (DSW). Glucose – 3 g/L, NH₄Cl – 0.5 g/L, KH₂PO₄ – 0.25 g/L, MgCl₂ – 0.3 g/L, CoCl₂ – 25 mg/L, ZnCl₂ – 11.5 mg/L, CaCl₂ – 5 mg/L, were added as micronutrients. Slurry containing mix anaerobic bacteria was added 400 ml/L of wastewater. The characteristics of municipal sewage wastewater (MW) were as follows :

- pH – 6.97
- BOD mg/L – 180
- COD mg/L – 225

After setting of experiment all dual-chambered mediators less MFCs were operated with four different anodes i.e. CC, GrR, CP and WC electrodes in same conditions, as feed to support the formation of biomass and subsequent generation of electricity. The MFCs were continuously monitored during experiment and readings were taken, inoculum time was considered as time 0. When MFCs were inoculated with sewage wastewater samples, there was about 24 h lag phase followed by an increase in cell current. The initial current generation here can be attributed to the presence of components that are easily utilized by mixed micro organism's presents in the wastewaters. When these easily degradable substrates were exhausted, the current generation may be due to the degradation of complex components. We compare the results of all electrodes and find that CC gives best results than all other electrodes.

Analytical measurements and calculations :

Voltages were measured at time intervals of 20 min across an external resistance (2 ohm) using multimeter Philips. The current was measured by $I = V/R$, where I is current (Ampere), V is voltage (Volt) and R is the applied external resistance (Ω). The power densities

were calculated by using $P = R \times I^2 / A$, where I is the current (Ampere), A is the area of electrode and R is applied external resistance (Ω)³⁰.

BOD and COD were measured according to the dichromate method^{31,32}. COD removal (%) was calculated based on the initial and final COD. The coulombic efficiency (CE) was calculated as the current over time until the maximum theoretical current was achieved. The evaluated CE over time was calculated with the following eq. (iii) :

$$CE = \frac{M \int_0^t Idt}{Fb v_{an} \Delta COD} \quad (iii)$$

where M is the molecular weight of oxygen (32), F is Faraday's constant, $b = 4$ indicates the number of electrons exchanged per mole of oxygen, v_{an} is the volume of liquid in the anode compartment, and ΔCOD is the change in the Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) over time, ' t '.

To measure the stability and efficiency of CC electrode, a substrate i.e. sewage waste was used to monitor the current and power out-put upto lower value production. To find out the degradation period of electrode a control test was run without refueling of substrate that produce current upto 30 days. Once the current output decreased to the lower value a new feed was introduced into the reactor until very low value (0.2 A) of current was observed³³. To measure the bio-fouling of anodic chamber on the electrode, the change in resistance of electrode material is measured by i-V characteristics at different time intervals of the experiment.

After the completion of 30 days MFCs were disassembled, rinsed with water and immediately fixed adherent bacteria on the anode with 2% glutaraldehyde solution overnight at 4 °C for bacterial fixation and SEM imaging. Samples were then dehydrated by serial, 10 min transfers through 20, 40, 60, 80 and 100% ethanol. Fixed samples were examined using SEM (JEOL ISM 840).

Conclusion

In the present study microbial fuel cell technology was successfully applied for the generation of electricity by using wastewater. Among all electrodes (CC, GrR, CP, WC) used in study the carbon cloth both as

anode and cathode shows good results with stability. Good results were observed for carbon cloth electrode because it possesses good biocompatibility (no microbial toxicity), high electro catalytic activity towards the oxidation of various metabolites, chemical and electrochemical stability as well as high, stability against bio-fouling, insensitivity against poisoning by biological products and low costs. The results suggest that MFC technology is profitable for practical use of wastewater treatment and electricity generation in the future and will become a preferred option among sustainable bioenergy processes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor R. K. Sharma, Department of Chemistry, Delhi University, Delhi for laboratory facilities.

References

1. Y. Ye, X. Zhu and B. E. Logan, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2016, **194**, 441.
2. W. Yang, J. Li, D. Ye, L. Zhang, X. Zhu and Q. Liao, *J. Power Sources*, 2016, **306**, 685.
3. F. L. Lobo, H. Wang, C. Forrestal and Z. J. Ren, *J. Power Sources*, 2015, **297**, 252.
4. H. B. Shen, X. Y. Yong, Y. L. Chen, Z. H. Liao, R. W. Si, J. Zhou, S. Y. Wang, Y. C. Yong, P. K. O. Yang and T. Zheng, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2014, **167**, 490.
5. B. E. Logan and K. Rabaey, *Sci.*, 2012, **337**, 686.
6. A. Mehdinia, E. Ziaei and A. Jabbari, *Electrochim. Acta*, 2014, **130**, 512.
7. Y. Fan, H. Hu and H. Liu, *J. Power Sources*, 2007, **171**, 348.
8. B. Logan, S. Cheng, V. Watson and G. Estadt, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2007, **41**, 3341.
9. X. Cao, X. Huang, P. Liang, K. Xiao, Y. Zhou, X. Zhang and B. E. Logan, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2009, **43**, 7148.
10. X. Cao, X. Huang, X. Zhang, P. Liang and M. Fan, *Environ. Sci. Eng.*, 2009, **3**, 307.
11. K. Rabaey, N. Boon, S. D. Siciliano, M. Verhaege and W. Verstraete, *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.*, 2004, **70**, 5373.
12. Y. Qiao, C. M. Li, S. J. Bao and Q. L. Bao, *J. Power Sources*, 2007, **170**, 79.
13. Y. C. Yong, X. C. Dong, M. B. Chan-Park, H. Song and P. Chen, *ACS Nano*, 2012, **6**, 2394.
14. M. Zhou, M. Chi, H. Wang and T. Jin, *Biochem. Eng. J.*, 2012, **60**, 151.
15. J. Ji, Y. Jia, W. Wu, L. Bai, L. Ge and Z. Gu, *Colloids Surf. (A)*, 2011, **390**, 56.
16. J. Wei, P. Liang and X. Huang, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2011, **102**, 9335.
17. B. Lai, X. Tang, H. Li, Z. Du, X. Liu and Q. Zhang, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2011, **28**, 373.
18. Y. Qiao, S. J. Bao, C. M. Li, X. Q. Cui, Z. S. Lu and J. Guo, *ACS Nano*, 2007, **2**, 113.
19. D. H. Park and J. G. Zeikus, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 2002, **59**, 58.
20. J. R. Kim, S. H. Jung, J. M. Regan and B. E. Logan, *Bioresour. Technol.*, 2007, **98**, 2568.
21. S. Cheng and B. E. Logan, *Electrochem. Commun.*, 2007, **9**, 492.
22. H. Zhang, R. Zhang, G. Zhang, F. Yang and F. Gao, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*, 2014, **39**, 11250.
23. K. Rabaey, G. Lissens, S. Siciliano and W. Verstraete, *Biotechnol. Lett.*, 2003, **25**, 1531.
24. S. K. Chaudhuri and D. R. Lovley, *Nat. Biotech.*, 2003, **21**, 1229.
25. K. Rabaey, P. Clauwaert, P. Aelterman and W. Verstraete, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2005, **39**, 8077.
26. X. Jiaa, Z. Hea, X. Zhang and X. Tian, *Synthetic Metals*, 2016, **215**, 170.
27. Z. Lv, D. Xie, X. Yue, C. Feng and C. Wei, *J. Power Sources*, 2012, **210**, 26.
28. P. Clauwaert, K. Rabaey, P. Aelterman, L. De Schampelaire, T. H. Pham, P. Boeckx, N. Boon and W. Verstraete, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2007, **41**, 3354.
29. Y. Chen, L. Chen, P. Li, Y. Xu, M. Fan, S. Zhu and S. Shen, *Energy*, 2016, **109**, 620.
30. H. Y. Tsai, C. C. Wu, C. Y. Lee and E. P. Shih, *J. Power Sources*, 2009, **194**, 199.
31. Y. Aifei, F. Yali, T. Zhuwei and L. Haoran, *Int. J. Electrochem. Sci.*, 2015, **10**, 1459.
32. A. Greenberg, L. S. Clesceri and A. D. Eaton, 18th ed., American Public Health Association, Washington DC, 1992.
33. B. R. Ringeisen, E. Henderson, P. K. Wu, J. Pietron, R. Ray, B. Little, C. Biffinger and J. M. Jones-Meehan, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2006, **40**, 2629.
34. R. N. Goyal, V. K. Gupta and N. Bachheti, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2007, **597**, 82.
35. R. Jain, V. K. Gupta, N. Jadon and K. Radhapyari, *Anal. Biochem.*, 2010, **407**, 79.
36. M. M. Barsan, E. M. Pinto, M. Florescu and C. M. A. Brett, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2009, **635**, 71.
37. S. Khilari, S. Pandit, D. Das and D. Pradhan, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2014, **54**, 534.
38. I. S. Chang, J. K. Jang, G. C. Gil, M. Kim, H. J. Kim, B. W. Cho and B. H. Kim, *Biosens. Bioelectron.*, 2004, **19**, 607.